

**“STUDY OF PEDIATRIC SEPTOPLASTY AND ITS
OUTCOMES”**

Submitted by

Dr.SUREKHA M.B.B.S.

Dissertation submitted to the
**B.L.D.E (Deemed to be University),
VIJAYAPURA, KARNATAKA.**

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

MASTER OF SURGERY

In

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

Under the guidance of

DR. H.T.LATHADEVI

PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF
OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY,

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE,

VIJAYAPURA, KARNATAKA.

2024

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.**

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I at this moment declare that this dissertation entitled “ **STUDY OF PEDIATRIC SEPTOPLASTY AND ITS OUTCOMES**” is a bonafide and genuine research work carried out by me under the guidance of **Dr.H.T.LATHADEVI**, Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology at B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be university), Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka.

Surakha

Date:

SIGNITURE OF STUDENT

Place:

Post Graduate student,

Department of Otorhinolaryngology

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical

College, Hospital & Research Centre,

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.**

CERTIFICATE BY THE GUIDE

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**STUDY OF PEDIATRIC SEPTOPLASTY AND ITS OUTCOMES**” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr.SUREKHA** in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of M.S. in Otorhinolaryngology.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura, Karnataka.

H.T. Lathadevi

Signature of the Guide :

Dr.H.T.LATHADEVI

Professor,

Department of Otorhinolaryngology,

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B.M. Patil

Medical College, Hospital & Research

Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

ENDORSEMENT BY HEAD OF DEPARTMENT AND PRINCIPAL

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**STUDY OF PEDIATRIC SEPTOPLASTY AND ITS OUTCOMES**” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr. SUREKHA** under the guidance of **DR. H.T.LATHADEVI**, Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology at BLDE (Deemed to be university), Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka

Seal & Signature of HOD

Dr. R.N.KARADI M.S.,

Professor and Head of

Department,

Otorhinolaryngology,

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B.M.

Patil Medical College,

Hospital & Research

Centre, Vijayapura.

Seal & Signature of Principal

Dr. ARAVIND PATIL M.S., Principal
& Dean,

Faculty of Medicine,

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B.M. Patil Medical

College, Hospital & Research Centre,

Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura.

COPYRIGHT

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I hereby declare that the B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University), Vijayapura, shall have the rights to preserve, use and disseminate this dissertation in print or electronic format for academic/research purpose.

Date: **Signature of the Candidate**

Surekha

Place: Vijayapura, Karnataka

DR.SUREKHA M.B.B.S.

Post Graduate student,

Department of Otorhinolaryngology

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical

College, Hospital & Research Centre,

Vijayapura, Karnataka

© BLDE (Deemed to be University), Karnataka

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It is with glorious veneration and intense gratitude I would like to thank my esteemed teacher and guide **Dr.H.T.LATHADEVI**, Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU)'s Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura: who was ever encouraging in her approach while helping me through my postgraduate course. She was always supportive and allowed me to work and develop at my own pace, guiding me wherever necessary. Without her guidance and support, it would have been impossible to complete this dissertation. I express my sincere gratitude to **DR.R.N.KARADI**, Professor and Head of Department, Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, for his support and encouragement throughout the preparation of the work.

I am immensely thankful to **Dr. Aravind Patil**, Principal, BLDE (DU) Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, for allowing me to do this work, to use facilities in this institution and for his encouragement and support throughout my postgraduate course

I am highly indebted to **Dr. S.P. Guggarigoudar**, Retired Principal and Head of Department, Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura for his valuable guidance and support throughout my postgraduate course in acquiring clinical knowledge.

I express my sincere gratitude to Associate professor, Dr.Venkatesh patil, Assitant professors, **Dr. Shashi Kumar and Dr.Nithin.P.S , Dr.Manali Bhat, Dr.shivshankar ajur**, senior residents, **Dr. Swetha.S Dr.Shanmukh, Dr.Anuja, Dr.sunita, Dr.sharanabassu** Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, for their concern, suggestions and constructive encouragement.

I am immensely thankful to my Postgraduate colleagues and friends, **Dr. Bhavya, Dr. Harika, Dr. Neethu, Dr. Arpitha, Dr.Indumathi, Dr. Mohan Raaj , Dr. Justin , Dr Ashwini patil, Dr.Radhika krishnan, Dr.Sushma , Dr.Sagarika , Dr. Reshma , Dr. Adishree , Dr.Nivedha, Dr.meghana,Dr.manisha,Dr.amit,Dr.tomin,Dr.neelima** for their immense help and support during my postgraduate course.

I am eternally grateful to my beloved family; my parents **Mr.N. Sunkireddy** and **Mrs N.Sarada** who have nurtured me and supported me in all my endeavours, without their love and innumerable sacrifices, I would not be the person I am today.

I would like to thank, Audiologists **Mr. Fakiriah**, Statisticians **Mrs. Vijaya Sorganvi**, Asst. Librarian for their support during my post graduate course. I am filled with gratitude to all my study subjects whose co-operation has contributed to this study.

Finally, I bow my head in a silent acknowledgement of all that **The Lord Almighty** has blessed me.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura,

Karnataka.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

%	Percentage
POD	Post Operative Day
NOSE	Nasal Obstruction Symptom Evaluation
CT	Computed Tomography
DNS	Deviated nasal septum
ITH	Inferior turbinate hypertrophy
DNE	Diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy
VAS	Visual Analogue Scale
AR	Allergic Rhinitis

LIST OF TABLES

Table (a)	Absolute & Relative indications of Pediatric Septoplasty
Table 1	Distribution of patients according to age
Table 2	Distribution of patients according to sex
Table 3	Distribution of patients according to h/o trauma
Table 4	Distribution of patients according to presence of symptoms of allergy
Table 5	Distribution of patients based on symptoms of allergy
Table 6	Distribution of patients according to deviation of septum
Table 7	Distribution of patients based on presence of ith
Table 8	Distribution of patients according to pre op nose scale score
Table 9	Distribution of patients according to pre op vas score
Table 10	Distribution of patients according to pod 7 nose score
Table 11	Distribution of patients according to pod 6 weeks nose scale score
Table 12	Distribution of patients according to pod 6 weeks vas score
Table 13	Nose scale pre operatively and post op 6 weeks
Table 14	Vas score pre operatively and post op 6 weeks
Table 15	Distribution of patients according to complications post surgery

LIST OF FIGURES

FIG 1	Anatomy of nasal septum
FIG 2	Blood supply of nasal septum
FIG 3	Nerve supply of nasal septum
FIG 4	Anterior rhinoscopy showing left dns with right ith
FIG 5	Dne showing nasal spur towards left
FIG 6	CT nose and PNS showing left dns with spur
FIG 7	Intra op image of Septoplasty
FIG 8	Nose scale score
FIG 9	VAS score

ABSTRACT

Background: A deviated nasal septum is an abnormal configuration of septal cartilage which may cause problems with breathing or nasal discharge.¹ A septal deviation can be present at the time of birth or can be caused by an injury. Incidence of DNS in pediatric patients is 59%. Exact timing for septoplasty among children remains unclear at present, because nasal growth completion occurs up to the age of 16 years in males and 14 years in females.² However, few centres have recently opted for an earlier age septoplasty when indicated only if it is considered that benefits are outweighing the risks. It is reported that Septoplasty surgery is successful in children. But this surgery must be conservative and must be restricted to pathologic area. Henceforth, this study is undertaken to compare the efficacy of septoplasty in pediatric age group who has nasal obstruction and poor quality of life.³

Aims:

- Study of Outcomes in children who underwent pediatric septoplasty in terms of nasal obstruction
- Quality of life assessment through Nose scale score.

Methodology: METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

1. The data will be collected in the form of a questionnaire in terms of complete clinical history, clinical examination and necessary investigations of the patients
2. Detailed examination of the patient with an emphasis on anterior rhinoscopy findings will be done with the help of thudicum nasal speculum or tip test and headlight to see the status of turbinate.
3. A preoperative diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy has been performed with 0 degrees and 30-degree scopes for cooperative patients.
4. Computed Tomography of Paranasal sinuses (coronal) Plain has been added 0.6 or 0.7mmPlain)
5. NOSE scale is used to assess the degree of nasal obstruction preoperatively and postoperatively.

6. A postoperative diagnostic nasal endoscopy has been performed with 0-degree and 30-degree scopes.
7. Post operatively patients are followed at 4 weeks and 6 weeks interval to assess the symptoms.
8. Randomization of the patients will be done by lottery methods. Chits will be given to the patients, and the patient is asked to select one chit to avoid bias for surgery.

Results: out of 30 patients, males were 76.7% and females were 23.3%. The current study reveals significant differences in post operative NOSE score and VAS score when compared to pre operative scores. This comparison was done using Wilcoxon test which showed considerable improvement in NOSE score and VAS score with significance <0.001 .

In the study synechia, infection following crust formation, and residual deviation were the common complications.

Conclusion: It is justified that septoplasty in the pediatric age group shows significant improvement in quality of life and the low complication rate, even if considerable cartilage work was done.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SR .NO	TITLE	PAGE NUMBER
1	Introduction	14
2	Aims & Objective	15
3	Review of literature	16-42
4	Materials and Methods	43-45
5	Results and Observations	46-55
6	Discussion	56-61
7	Conclusion	62
8	References	63-65
9	Annexures I Ethical Clearance Certificate II Proforma III. Consent form IV. Key to master chart V. Master chart	 66 67-70 71-77 78 79-83

INTRODUCTION

The most common complaint among patients visiting otorhinologists is prolonged nasal blockage. Nasal septal abnormalities and mucosal disease associated with turbinate hypertrophy can lead to nasal obstruction.¹ The septum, made of cartilage, divides the nose into two separate nasal cavities. A deviated nasal septum (DNS) is an abnormal configuration of the septal cartilage that divide these cavities, potentially causing breathing difficulties and nasal discharge. DNS can be congenital, result from injury, or arise from damage due to previous medical treatments. Trauma, a frequent cause of DNS, may occur during childbirth, especially with forceps placement or in patients with a narrow pelvic passage, where excessive pressure is exerted on the nose or midfacial area of the head.²

The symptoms of DNS, which include nasal obstruction, mouth breathing, increased airflow resistance, the unsightly look of the nose, and occasionally snoring, are significant in a child's life. In addition to nasal blockage, DNS in children can result in mechanical obstruction to the paranasal sinus's drainage, which can lead to postnasal drip, crusting, epistaxis, and recurrent sinusitis. A paediatric patient's long-term alleviation from this morbidity will be aided by early DNS diagnosis and care.³ A deviated nasal septum, which can be brought on by trauma or after birth, and is a condition in which the septum separates from the centre of the nose. Still, it is typical to deviate slightly to one side. until roughly the age of seven, the septum often remains in the midline; beyond that, it frequently veers to one side. Septoplasty is the term for the procedure used to straighten the nasal septum. Since nose development completion occurs at age 16 for males and 14 for females, the current state of septoplasty in children is unknown. When necessary, septoplasty is performed at an earlier age if the advantages outweigh the dangers. Children can have nasal septal surgery without having their midfacial and nasal development disrupted.⁴

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- Study of Outcomes in children who underwent pediatric septoplasty in terms of nasal obstruction
- Quality of life assessment through Nose scale score.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HISTORY :

3500 BC: The *Ebers Papyrus*, which has the first known mention of rhinologic surgery, was written during this time in Egypt. These reconstructive procedures like rhinectomy were considered as a form of punishment those days.

1757: Quelmatz was one of the earliest doctors to look into the septal deformities. He suggested applying daily digital pressure to the septum.

Adams had suggested breaking and splinting the nasal septum in 1875.

Late 19th century: The Bosworth operation was the standard procedure in the US.

The mucosa was removed along with the deviation using a specialised saw.

The outcomes weren't perfect. En bloc excision of tiny portions of septal cartilage was first described by Ingals in 1882. As a result, he is credited with founding contemporary septal surgery.

1899: Asch was the first person to recommend changing the septal cartilage's tensile curve rather than resection. Additionally, he suggested making full-thickness cruciate incisions.

1902 and 1904: The submucous resection (SMR) procedure was explained by Freer and Killian.

This is the basis for contemporary methods of septoplasty. They recommended elevating mucoperiosteal flaps and mucoperichondrial flaps resecting the bone and cartilaginous tissue, (including the vomer and the ethmoid's perpendicular plate), leaving 1 cm dorsally and 1 cm caudally in order to keep support.⁶

1929: With the assistance of Metzenbaum and Peer, the caudal septum was initially modified. It was discovered that the traditional SMR was less successful in addressing it.⁷ Furthermore, Metzenbaum recommended applying the swinging door method, and in 1937,

Peer recommended the caudal septum should be removed, straightened, and then replaced in the midpoint placement.

1947: Cottle proposed the use of the hemitransfixion incision and introduced it and careful resections of the septum. When a lengthy follow-up investigation was conducted on individuals who had undergone SMR, it was found that many of the individuals exhibited dorsal saddling, retraction of the columella. Surgical resections during septoplasty were therefore targeted to address columella and alar widening to stay clear of these issues.

In 2021, Ryan Bishop, Rishabh Sethia, Charles A. Elmaraghy et al., conducted a study to examine the long-term results of a sizable cohort of children who had nasal septoplasty and to compare the results of the procedure between patients under the age of 14 and those over that age.⁸

All patients who underwent nasal septoplasty at their paediatric referral centre between October 2009 and September 2016 were included in a retrospective research that was conducted. This analysis included all individuals who had undergone septoplasty for a deviated nasal septum and who were between the ages of 0 and 18 at the time of surgery. Results were compared between individuals younger than 14 and those older than 14 years of age. Data on follow-up, operation, and demographics were gathered, along with information on complications and the requirement for revision surgery.

It was discovered that a total of 194 paediatric patients satisfied the study's inclusion requirements. With a mean of 15.9 years in the older age group and 10.6 years in the younger the mean age was 14.6 years (0–18 years). The rate of problems did not, however, differ significantly between the two groups.⁹

In 2019, Jeyasakthy Saniasiaya, Baharudin Abdulla, et al. did a study on children's quality of life after nasal septal surgery and reviewed the results. After septoplasty, their quality of life in the paediatric age range has been well documented. Evaluations of paediatric septoplasty have produced encouraging

results. Can et al. proposed in their prospective study that acoustic rhinometry is an effective objective method for gauging the results of paediatric septoplasty.

According to a research by Anderson et al., there was a statistically significant improvement in health-related Quality of life following septoplasty, indicating a positive overall outcome.

Afterwards, the G.C.B.I. was used for scoring, with the physical subscore being the most important. Physical health improved when septal deviation was corrected because there was less obstruction to nasal airflow.¹⁰ A postoperative and preoperative global QoL-based VAS and SN-5 were used in Retrospective case series by Lee et al., on short-term QoL following paediatric septoplasty. A postoperatively observed significant improvement in the overall score was observed. After surgery, female patients had better short-term results than male ones.

Using the NOSE scale, Manteghi et al. conducted a prospective cohort research on the quality of life of paediatric patients before and after functional septorhinoplasty and septoplasty. The findings showed that paediatric patients' disease-specific quality of life improved statistically significantly following septoplasty and septorhinoplasty. Following septoplasty and reconstructive nasal deformity, recent anthropometric studies have indicated that paediatric patients have normal face and nasal growth. On the other hand, if corrective septal surgery has been postponed, children with considerable nasal obstruction had been documented to have deformities of the nose and face. Furthermore, they disclosed adverse impacts on the organs accountable for physical and mental growth, such as disturbed speech and disturbed sleep.¹¹

In the paediatric age range of 8 to 12 years, appropriate, cautious, and conservative nasal septal and reconstructive surgery has been demonstrated to be

successful, with no distortion in facial growth. Ignazio Tasca, Giacomo Ceroni Compadretti, et al. conducted a retrospective investigation on nasal growth in 2011 and assessed the results of paediatric septoplasty. They also conducted an anthropometric long-term follow-up. Forty-four Italian patients, 25 of whom were male and 19 of who were female, have been included in the study. All of the patients received endonasal septoplasty as children.

Afterwards, following an average follow-up of 12.2 years, they were reviewed.¹² Anthropometric recordings were found to be helpful in identifying any growth retardation resulting from the operation through comparison with age-specific normative data of white North American participants that had previously been published. With the exception of the nasal angle measurement, none of the nasal measurements revealed a significant gender difference ($p > 0.1$) between the sample and controls. The nasal measurements included five linear parameters, three angular parameters, and three proportional indexes.¹³ In fact, the female patients' nasolabial angle was considerable smaller than the controls' ($p = 0.04$), whereas the male patients' was smaller than the controls' ($p = 0.08$). The nasolabial angle of patients treated surgically with extracorporeal septoplasty was found to be significantly lower than that of patients treated surgically with conservative septoplasty. Consequently no significant difference is found any of the parameters of the study ($p > 0.1$). They came to the conclusion that, in certain situations of severe nasal obstruction, septoplasty may be appropriate for children in this age group. When the endonasal route is used for the operation, it does not disrupt the typical course of nose growth.

EMBRYOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT :

The ethmovomerine cartilage, a plate of cartilage, makes up the septum of the nose in the early stages of life. The anteroinferior component of this septal cartilage stays as septal cartilage, and the vomer is ossified in the membrane covering its posteroinferior part. The posterosuperior part of this cartilage is ossified to create the perpendicular plate of the ethmoid. The vomer is mostly made up of two lamellae, and there are two ossification centres in this area of the membrane, one on either side of the central line, that emerge during the eighth week of foetal development, these join below about the third month, creating a deep groove where the cartilage is trapped. The union of lamellae expands upward and forward during the growing phase, and at the same time, the cartilage plate that sits between them absorbs. By the time puberty arrives, the lamellae have nearly joined to create a median plate, but the groove on the anterior margin of the bone and the everted alae of its upper border show signs of the bone's bilaminar origin.

ANATOMY OF NASAL SEPTUM :

The nose's rough midline contains a bony and cartilaginous structure called the nasal septum. which divides the nostrils on the right and left (FIG 1).¹⁵ The nasal septum extends superiorly from the base of the skull to the nasal cavity in a sagittal plane. the nasal tip anteriorly to the sphenoid sinus and the nasopharynx posteriorly, and the hard palate inferiorly. Several bones contribute to the bony part of the septum. These plates are perpendicular. of the maxillary crest, which is made up of the maxillary and the vomer, the ethmoid bone, and bones in the palatine region. The caudal part of the septum is formed by the quadrangular cartilage. The perichondrium and periosteum are present between the osseous and cartilaginous sections of the septum. not connected. Medial wall of each nasal cavity is formed by nasal septum and contributes to internal and external nasal valves.¹⁶

[Anatomy of nasal septum. | Download Scientific diagram FIG 1](#)

BLOOD SUPPLY OF SEPTUM :

Because of the nose's abundant blood supply, inspired air can be successfully changed in terms of temperature and humidity.¹⁷ Both the internal and exterior carotid arteries contribute to it:(Figure2)

Internal carotid branches:

- Anterior ethmoidal artery
- Posterior ethmoidal artery

The ocular artery gives rise to the ethmoidal arteries. Through the cribriform plate, a sieve-like bone, they enter the nasal cavity.

External carotid branches:

Sphenopalatine artery

Greater palatine artery

Superior labial artery

Lateral nasal arteries

Apart from the abundant blood flow, these arteries also create anastomoses with one another. The front region of the nose is where this is most common. The nose's veins run parallel to the arteries. They empty into the cavernous sinus, facial vein, or pterygoid plexus. A small percentage of people have a nasal vein link with the dural venous sinus known as the sagittal sinus. This is among the possible routes via which any pathogen could enter the cerebral cavity through the nose.¹⁸

[The Nasal Cavity - Structure - Vasculature - Innervation ... FIG 2](#)

A brief description of nerve supply of nasal septum was given in FIG 3

NERVE SUPPLY OF NASAL SEPTUM:

[Otorhinolaryngology© | Download Scientific Diagram FIG 3](#)

DEVIATED NASAL SEPTUM

The term "deviated nasal septum" (DNS) refers to a deviation of the nasal septum's bone or cartilage, or both, from the face's midline.

CLASSIFICATION OF DNS

There are several types of DNS such

Type I: A slight deviation of the nasal septum in the vertical or horizontal plane that does not stretch through the vertical dimension of the nasal septum;

Type II: Vertical anterior deviation;

Type III: Vertical posterior deviation;

Type IV: S-shaped nasal septum;

Type V: Horizontal deviation on one side with or without distortion on the opposite side;

Type VI: Type V with a deep groove on the concave surface

Type VII: Any combination of Types II to VI.

There is also an another classification of septal deviation angle according to degree of its deviation.³³

- | | |
|---------------------|---|
| Type I (normal)- | naso septal angle less than 5 degree. |
| Type II (mild) - | naso septal angle from 5 degrees to 10 degrees |
| Type III moderate)- | naso septal angle from 10 degrees to 15 degrees |
| Type IV(severe)- | naso septal angle more than 15 degrees. |

Cottle et al classified DNS into 4 types. They are: subluxation, large spur, caudal deflection and tension septum.¹⁹ Guyuron et al classified DNS into six types. They are: Septal tilt, anteroposterior C-shaped, cephalocaudal C-shaped, anteroposterior S-shaped, cephalocaudal S-shaped, and wide spur.

DNS can be classified on the basis of position or location of the deviation into anterior and posterior deviation. In clinical practice, anterior DNS is more common. A detailed assessment of the nasal septum is crucial for surgical planning, function restoration, and reevaluating aesthetic concerns.

CLINICAL PRESENTATION:

Many children with DNS experience minimal or no symptoms at all. On the other hand, children with gross DNS experience systemic, physiological, anatomical, psychological, and cosmetic issues. It results in nasal blockage, which makes feeding a newborn baby difficult or delayed and produces colic because of aerophagy.²⁰ In a baby, severe nasal blockage caused by DNS mimics choanal atresia and its aftereffects. Children with DNS may experience nasal obstruction, mouth breathing, rhinorrhea, epistaxis, hypo- or anosmia, and other symptoms. In addition to poor general health, it can cause sinusitis, epistaxis, eustachian tube dysfunction, chronic otitis media, facial asymmetry, dental malalignments, and malocclusions. Numerous reports demonstrate that middle ear conditions, palatal asymmetry, malocclusion, dental abnormalities, and even recurring upper respiratory tract infections are seen in children with DNS. Due to turbinate prominence, children who have nasal septal deviation on one side may experience paradoxical nasal obstruction, which is the complaint of nasal blockage on the contralateral side. This leads to a depressed tongue and open mouth, which eventually results in less tone in the maxillofacial muscles.²¹

It will therefore have an impact on midfacial growth, resulting in maxillary hypoplasia, retrognathia, micrognathia, and upper incisor protrusion. There is a decrease in the posterior face height but an increase in the anterior lower vertical face height. Negative consequences have also been documented, including altered psychological and somatic development, which includes vocal disturbance.²²

DIAGNOSIS:

Making a clinical diagnosis of DNS is simple. (FIG 4 shows left dns) DNS is frequently diagnosed based on clinical presentation and examination results. In the Cottle's manoeuvre test, the nasal valve is opened by pulling the cheek laterally with one or two fingers. This test helps identify if the nasal blockage caused by DNS is closer to the nasal cavity's interior or at the valve location. Prior to surgical planning, children with DNS should have a computed tomography (CT) scan of their nose and paranasal sinuses.²³

The best method for diagnosing DNS is to employ diagnostic fiber optic nasal endoscopy (fig 5 shows dne picture of a nasal spur) in conjunction with a CT scan of the paranasal sinuses and nose. This combination is particularly helpful in ruling out inflammatory diseases including sinusitis and mass lesions in the nose and sinuses. Coronal and axial CT scans of the nose and paranasal sinuses (fig 6 shows CT picture of nose and pns showing left dns with spur) can be used to quickly identify a DNS. For a direct assessment of the DNS, additional three-dimensional images of the midline structure are useful. Rhinomanometry is a helpful technique for evaluating nasal cavity airflow. This test is helpful in assessing how well nasal airflow has improved after nasal septal correction surgery for DNS.²⁴

ANTERIOR RHINOSCOPY SHOWING LEFT DNS WITH RIGHT ITH (FIG 4)

DNE SHOWING NASAL SPUR TOWARDS LEFT (FIG 5)

CT NOSE AND PNS SHOWING LEFT DNS WITH SPUR (FIG 6)

Children's nasal septal surgery is controversial due to its detrimental impact on the development of the craniofacial structure. Nonetheless, the unavoidable result of nasal septal surgery is midfacial and nasal growth distortion, which can be avoided with early nasal septal correction. It has been demonstrated that nasal septal surgery significantly improves quality of life in children. One significant surgical option for treating the nasal septal defect is septoplasty. Restoring the nasal cavity's patency is the primary goal of treating DNS in infants.²⁵ For children with DNS, the preferred surgical procedure is septoplasty. Despite being safe, septoplasty can occasionally result in issues with nasal and facial growth. Among otolaryngologists, this causes considerable disagreement when it comes to treating pediatric DNS. When children undergo surgery for DNS before reaching adolescence, the procedure should only involve the resection of an obstructing spur or the realignment of the septum with minimal cartilage resection in order to avoid impairing the growth of the nasal pyramid. The clinical indications for the procedure should also be very well-founded.²⁶

Early childhood correction of severe traumatic nasal septal deviation can prevent future nasal and systemic problems. Numerous otolaryngologists have successfully operated on the nasal septum during the first one to two days of a baby's life by providing closed manipulation. This method is often only used for anterior cartilage subluxations that are identified either right away or very soon after childbirth. In a conservative surgical treatment known as a septoplasty, the bony crests are just trimmed and refractured to the medial position, leaving the bony septum intact. The deviated septal cartilage is removed. The growth of the nasal septum's quadrangular cartilage ceases around the age of five to six, while the bony components, like the vomer and perpendicular lamina, continue to grow until puberty. Therefore, it is recommended that the bony portion of the nasal septum not be removed in patients with DNS who are between the ages of 5 and 16 in order to prevent any reduction in

active facial growth and changes to the naso facial development. Conversely, resection of the cartilaginous component of the nasal septum is possible, albeit cautious resection.²⁷ At the moment, otolaryngologists only remove enough septal cartilage to open up the nasal airway—not enough to compromise the dorsal support or impair the development of the craniofacial structure after surgery. Some surgeons attempt to create a single tunnel on the left side of the septal cartilage. This is made possible by the septal cartilage's elasticity and flexibility, which cause the cartilage to straighten once the excess length and height are removed a process that may be completed with a single tunnel technique. A low rate of problems is a characteristic of this single tube approach. This technique reduces the risk of postoperative septal haemorrhage and septal perforation while maintaining the blood supply to the right side cartilage by leaving the mucoperichondrium intact with septal cartilage. It is crucial to notify parents or other carers of a child's DNS in order to prevent developmental issues like snoring, facial growth, and recurring upper respiratory infections.²⁹

IMPACT OF SEPTAL SURGERY ON FACIAL GROWTH:

Children undergoing nasal surgery require specific anatomical and physiological understanding of nasal development. Currently, otolaryngologists only remove enough septal cartilage to facilitate nasal breathing; they do not remove enough to jeopardise the dorsal support or hinder the postoperative growth of the craniofacial structure. A single tunnel on the left side of the septal cartilage is what some surgeons try to accomplish. The elasticity and suppleness of the septal cartilage allow the cartilage to straighten once the extra length and height are removed, a procedure that can be finished with a single tunnel approach. One of the advantages of this single tube technique is its low trouble rate. The mandibular arch, frontonasal process, and membranous components make up the midface region. The nose and midface continue to grow until the ages of 14 to 17. On the other hand, it has been shown that the nasal septum grows until the age of 36.³⁰

As one grows older, their nose changes in shape.⁴⁵ The face's growth centre is the nasal septum. Both the sphenodorsal and sphenospinal growth zones are seen. While the sphenospinal zone is in charge of the forward expansion of the premaxillar area and is accountable for sagittal growth, the sphenodorsal zone is in charge of the typical rise in length and height of the nose's dorsum. Care must be taken while planning corrective nasal septal surgery in youngsters in order to prevent severe facial deformities that might require additional surgery, nasal reconstruction surgery.

According to a contrast report, children who had delayed corrective septal surgery and had considerable nasal blockage had facial and nasal deformities.³ In younger age group between 8 and 12 years, careful and conservative nasal septal surgery has been shown to be successful with no signs of facial deformity. Children who had surgery severe years prior did not have any nasal septal abnormality throughout the follow-up. According to one study, female patients get higher results and symptom relief than their male counterparts. Both younger and older children's symptoms have improved equally in relation to their age. Comparing open and closed surgical techniques, there was no discernible improvement, supporting the less invasive endoscopic method for septoplasty.³²

SEPTOPLASTY IN CHILDREN :

There will be little alterations to the nasal skeleton and septum's size and composition during development. A paediatric nose's exterior features can be summed up as having a shorter nasal dorsum with less projection and a bigger nasolabial angle. Furthermore, a child's nasal tip is frequently flatter, with a short columella and rounded nares. There will be more cartilage to bone in the septum itself. The septal cartilage covers the columella and nasal tip after birth, which

extends from sphenoid bone at the level of base of the skull. The cartilaginous septum experiences progressive ossification, and the perpendicular plate grows in a caudoventral orientation.³³

Following the completion of the perpendicular plate expansion, the spinoseptal ligament (decussating fibres) securely joins the septal cartilage to the premaxilla, separating it from the sphenoid. At two years of life, the septum's cartilaginous dimensions reach their peak. After this stage, the septum grows because the perpendicular plate grows as a result of the septal cartilage at the septo ethmoidal junction continuing to osseously expand. Ossification-induced cartilage loss is counterbalanced by mitotic activity and intracellular matrix growth, which produce new cartilage. In addition, the upper lateral cartilages of children's noses extend under the nasal bones' length, whereas in adults' noses, they only do so 3 to 5 mm below the nasal bones. The child's growing upper lateral cartilages are the cause of this transformation.³⁴

Furthermore, a number of the typical adult bone structures—such as the vomer—are undeveloped in paediatric patients. The perpendicular plate and vomer will fully mature and merge at the age of 6 to 8 years old. There are two distinct phases of notable nasal development. As previously mentioned, the first phase occurs throughout the first two years of life. During puberty, the second phase lasts from the ages of 12 to 16 for girls and 15 to 18 for boys. Consequently, historically, elective surgery was postponed until a boy's or girl's age of 17 or 14, so as to allow the nose to fully mature before operation. The sphenodorsal zone, which lies between the sphenoid and dorsum, and the sphenospinal zone, which lies between the sphenoid and anterior nasal spine, are the two growth centres of the nose. The sphenospinal angle is in charge of the maxilla's forward expansion, whilst the sphenodorsal zone lengthens and heightens the nasal bones. In an observational research, these two zones and their impact on nose growth were assessed in a pair of monozygotic twins by Grymer et al. One twin experienced growth inhibition as a

result of trauma to these growth zones, and as a result, the nasal cavity's vertical height decreased, the anterior maxilla was displaced upward, and the maxilla became retrognathic due to a decrease in anteroposterior maxillary growth.³⁵

Timing

There is ongoing debate concerning the minimal age at which a septoplasty would be prudent. Septal deviation, however, can exist from birth. Trauma occurring during birth canal passage increases the risk of naso septal deformity.

Approximately 22% of children born spontaneously have deformed septa, compared to 3.9% of children born via caesarean section. Due to their preference nasal breathing, patients with nasoseptal malformation may experience respiratory discomfort and ultimately fail to flourish if treatment is not received. Many authors recommend delaying surgical intervention for nasal blockage until the child is 5 or 6 years old, even though septal deviation can manifest at a very young age. If there are other reasons for a septoplasty, the procedure can be required for children under the age of five. Treatment for nasal septal deviation in neonates is advised to involve closed reduction.³⁶

INDICATIONS:

Although it is normally recommended to postpone septoplasty until after nasal development is complete, there are a number of reasons why it can be done earlier. The absolute and relative indications for paediatric septoplasty are listed in (Table a). Paediatric septoplasty is indicated in all cases when there is a septal abscess with cartilage damage, significant nasal deformity from an acute nasal fracture, nasoseptal deformity from a cleft, nasal cancer, or severe nasal blockage that causes sleep apnea.

Due to the possibility of growing functional losses, anatomic deformity, and the psychological repercussions of postponing surgery, these criteria are generally acknowledged. If left untreated, severe malformations might result in palatal asymmetry, malocclusion, and other diverse midface and dental architecture deformities.³⁷

For cases of septal abscess, first line of treatment involves incision and drainage as well antibiotics. However, septoplasty does play a crucial role in reconstruction in case of infected as well as necrotic cartilage. By performing immediate reconstruction of the cartilage and correcting the deformity early, we can eliminate long term side effects on the growth of the midface. Alshaikh et al., assessed the role of septoplasty in cartilage reconstruction by reviewing results from 81 articles, and he had found that early reconstruction resulted in normal nasal development and function.

The most prevalent reason for doing septoplasty on children is nasal airway obstruction, which is also a relative indication for the treatment. While numerous studies have demonstrated that septoplasty in and of itself does not seem to have an impact on the growth of the craniofacial skeleton, other research has demonstrated that dental malocclusion, sinusitis, and abnormalities in the growth of the midface and nose can result from untreated nasal respiratory obstruction.³⁸ Particularly, it has been demonstrated that children who are forced to breathe through their mouths because to nasal blockage have taller upper and lower frontal faces, a wider gonial angle, and a retrognathic maxilla and mandible position. Additionally, substantial septal deviation can cause serious respiratory distress because newborns typically preferentially breathe through their noses until they are six months old. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that children's snoring, viral upper respiratory infections, bronchitis, and sinusitis are all more common when there is a septal deviation. It has also been demonstrated that persistent partial airway blockage might lead to systemic consequences including pulmonary hypertension. A

comprehensive assessment of the patient's complete upper airway is crucial for deciding whether or not they are a candidate for septoplasty based on the diagnosis of nasal airway blockage. While it is possible, it is uncommon for nasal septal deviation to be the only factor contributing to obstructive breathing.

When doing septoplasty for nasal airway blockage, it's critical to rule out alternative reasons, including hypertrophic adenoids, choanal atresia, and nasal tumours.³⁹ Paediatric patients may also present with diseases of the skull base, however these are rare. Treatment with endoscopic endonasal skull base surgery may necessitate concurrent septoplasty in order to gain access to the skull base. Last but not least, a recent study by Levi et al. demonstrated encouraging outcomes when septoplasty is utilised to treat children with recalcitrant idiopathic epistaxis. Twenty patients in this study underwent treatment with either conventional septoplasty or modified septoplasty, which involves elevating bilateral mucoperichondrial flaps without resecting any septal cartilage.

At their one-month follow-up, 18 out of the 20 patients had fully recovered from their epistaxis symptoms. If standard septoplasty techniques are used to address septal deviation, the pathophysiology of this treatment strategy is hypothesised to be associated with both a decrease in turbulent airflow and scarring of the causal vasculature on the raised mucoperichondrial flaps.⁴⁰

TABLE (a) ABSOLUTE AND RELATIVE INDICATIONS OF PEDIATRIC SEPTOPLASTY

ABSOLUTE INDICATIONS	RELATIVE INDICATIONS
1. Severe nasal obstruction leading to sleep apnea	Nasal airway obstruction
2. Severe nasal deformity secondary to nasal fracture	Recurrent idiopathic epistaxis
3. Septal abscess with necrosis of cartilage	Access to endo nasal fossa and skull base surgery
4. Septal deformity secondary to cleft	

TECHNIQUE:

Restoring normal anatomy, enhancing function, and encouraging normal nasal development should be the objectives of surgery. For paediatric patients undergoing a septoplasty, preservation surgery is the preferred procedure. Based on clinical observations and scientific evidence, Verwoerd and Verwoerd-Verhoef have issued guidelines for procedure while doing paediatric septoplasty. According to these recommendations, either unilateral or bilateral elevation of the mucoperichondrium to gain access to the cartilaginous septum does not impede the normal growth of the nose. To safeguard the incisive nerves, the mucosa of the nasal floor should not be elevated. Incisions through the important growth and support zones should also be avoided, with special emphasis to the sphenodorsal zone.⁴¹

As previously mentioned, damage to this zone may result in inhibited growth of the nasal dorsum in length and height. Posterior chondrotomy, or separation of the septum from the perpendicular plate, should be avoided when possible as it is thought this region is important in the development of length and height of the nasal septum and dorsum. However, resection of cartilaginous septum more anteriorly along the floor does not affect the outgrowth of the nasal dorsum. Transection of the septospinal ligament (decussating fibers) should be avoided to prevent unwanted forward growth of the maxilla. If the caudal rim of septal cartilage becomes subluxed, it should be repositioned into a columellar pocket and sutured between the medial crura. If cartilage is resected, it is preferable to replace with autologous septum or cartilage on a scaffold to prevent scarring between the bilateral mucoperichondrial flaps or septal perforation. If the upper lateral cartilages become separated from the septum, they should be re-approximated with sutures to prevent future deviations of the nasal dorsal cartilage.⁴² A popular biosynthetic material often now considered for use in the pediatric and adult population is the use of polydioxanone (PDS) plating or foil to prevent recurrent deviations and re-dislocation of grafts. PDS foil has also shown to stimulate some cartilage

regeneration. The use of proplast and gore-tex has largely fallen out of favor due to inflammation, growth inhibition and severe deformities of the nose and midface. Particular attention should be paid to the cranial base when performing pediatric septoplasty as ossification of the septum and cartilaginous cranial base is variable in children, making the cranial base more prone to injury.⁴³ Because children's vestibular areas are small, access to the paediatric septum might be challenging.

Because of this, it may be quite challenging to apply normal techniques employed with adults to a portion of the paediatric population. As a result, a sublabial technique is employed occasionally to reach the septum. Using the sublabial technique, an incision is created in the upper gingivolabial sulcus, roughly measuring the nasal base's breadth in length. Up until the anterior nasal spine is reached, the dissection is done superiorly. Next, there is a bilateral elevation of the quadrangular cartilage's mucoperichondrium. Nonetheless, the majority of kids don't need a sublabial approach, and their nasal development is frequently adequate for a traditional endonasal approach using an incision made by hemitransfixion or Killian. In order to prevent obvious scarring and post-operative scar contracture, care must be taken to avoid making the incision at the cutaneous part of the caudal septum. The usual nasolabial angle may change and columellar retraction may result from scar contracture.⁴⁴

Surgical procedure:

Following steps are usually done for pediatric septoplasty in this study:

- Surgery is done under general hypotensive anesthesia with patient in supine position and head elevated 45°.
- Following intubation, the endotracheal tube is secured to the chin at midline to ensure accurate assessment of facial symmetry.
- Lubricant eye ointment is placed bilaterally, after which each eyelid is closed

and secured using a transparent dressing.

- The caudal septum and nasal structures are injected with a solution of 2% lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine in a sub-mucoperichondrial plane ideally resulting in hydro- dissection. Two 0.5 × 3-in. cotton soft roll pledges soaked with 4% lignocaine mixed with adrenaline are then placed in each nasal cavity.
- A freer's incision- a unilateral hemitransfixation incision is made at the caudal border of the septum with a 15-mm blade.
- Mucoperichondrial and mucoperiosteal flaps are elevated, septal cartilage is visualized.
- A vertical incision is given over the cartilage and opposite side flaps elevated. Only deviated part of the septum is removed leaving the remaining septum intact.
- If spur is present, it is also removed.
- Then flaps are repositioned and sutured anteriorly with vicryl3-0.
- After achieving hemostasis, soframycin soaked nasal pack is placed in both the nasal cavities.
- Pack is removed on post operative day 1.
- Post operatively intravenous antibiotics are given for one to two days .
- Patient is made to stay in hospital for one to two days for observation and then discharged on oral antibiotics and pain killers.

Patient is asked to come for follow up on post operative day 7, after 4 weeks and then 6 weeks for assessment

OUTCOMES:

Stewart et al.'s nose obstruction symptom evaluation (NOSE) is one particular QOL tool that has been validated. This measure assesses a patient's symptoms, such as breathing difficulties, sleep disturbances, nasal congestion, nasal obstruction, and breathing during physical activity or exertion.⁴⁵ Depending on how serious the complaint is, each parameter is assigned a point between 0 and 4. The values of all the parameters are then summed, and the total is multiplied by 5.

We shall rank the results as follows:

mild (5-25),
moderate (30-50),
severe (55-75), and
extreme (80-100).

The nose scale score is displayed in FIG 8. Yilmaz et al.,²⁸ employed it to assess outcomes in the paediatric population, despite the fact that it was initially designed to track adult septoplasty outcomes. The postoperative NOSE ratings of their patient sample showed statistically significant improvement over baseline. Can et al. also measured minimal cross sectional areas (MCSA) and total volume (TV) during paediatric septoplasty using acoustic rhinometry.⁴⁶ These objective measurements are obtained via acoustic rhinometry, which uses reflections of sound pulses inserted through the nares into the nasal cavity. When Can et al. compared preoperative and postoperative values in patients who reported a subjective improvement in their symptoms, they discovered a statistically significant change in these measurements.⁴⁷

INTRA OPERATIVE IMAGE OF PEDIATRIC SEPTOPLASTY

(FIG 7) INTRA OP SEPTOPLASTY

NASAL OBSTRUCTION SYMPTOM EVALUATION SCALE SCORE:

Nasal Obstruction Symptom Evaluation (NOSE) Instrument

→ To the Patient Please help us to better understand the impact of nasal obstruction on your quality of life by **completing the following survey**. Thank You!

Over the past 1 month, how much of a problem were the following conditions for you?

Please circle the most correct response

	<i>Not a problem</i>	<i>Very mild problem</i>	<i>Moderate problem</i>	<i>Fairly bad problem</i>	<i>Severe problem</i>
1. Nasal congestion or stuffiness	0	1	2	3	4
2. Nasal blockage or obstruction	0	1	2	3	4
3. Trouble breathing through my nose	0	1	2	3	4
4. Trouble sleeping	0	1	2	3	4
5. Unable to get enough air through my nose during exercise or exertion	0	1	2	3	4

[https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fjournals.sagepub.com%2Fdoi%2F10.1177%2F01455613211015440%3Ficid%3Dint.sj-full-text.similar-articles.2&psig=AOvVaw3AfULfegdtOabfBjk4saos&ust=1720101030778000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBQQjhXqFwoTCMj3x-uBi4cDFQAAAAAdAAAAABA_\(FIG_8\)](https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fjournals.sagepub.com%2Fdoi%2F10.1177%2F01455613211015440%3Ficid%3Dint.sj-full-text.similar-articles.2&psig=AOvVaw3AfULfegdtOabfBjk4saos&ust=1720101030778000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBQQjhXqFwoTCMj3x-uBi4cDFQAAAAAdAAAAABA_(FIG_8))

VAS SCORE (VISUAL ANALOGUE SCALE):

Visual analogue scales (VAS) are psychometric measuring tools intended to quickly (statistically measurable and reproducibly) classify symptom severity and disease control by recording the features of disease-related symptom severity in individual patients. VAS is also useful for routinely recording a patient's medical history and tracking the progression of conditions like sinusitis, allergic rhinitis, and deviated nasal septum that can clog the nose. More precisely, evaluating and comparing the pre- and post-operative VAS scores for procedures like septoplasty, Fess, and AR therapy in order to determine the efficacy of the course of treatment.⁴⁸ VAS score is depicted in (FIG 9)

https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.researchgate.net%2Ffigure%2Fvisual-analogue-scale-of-nasal-obstruction_fig1_317190067&psig=AOvVaw3sz4zGaBab6WSy0qqYt5US&ust=1720102022653000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBQQjhxqFwoTCJi-5sGFi4cDFQAAAAAdAAAAABAE (FIG 9)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN : CROSS-SECTIONAL PROSPECTIVE STUDY

SOURCE OF DATA :

All children between 8 to 14 years who are undergoing septoplasty surgery in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology, B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University) Shri B. M . Medical College and research center, Vijayapura, between July 2022 to December 2023.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA:

1. A questionnaire is used to gather information on the patients' whole clinical history, clinical examination, and required investigations.
2. A thorough examination of the patient was conducted, focusing on the results of the anterior rhinoscopy. The turbinate's condition was assessed using a spotlight and a thudicum nasal speculum.
3. Both 0 degree and 30 degree scopes have been used for a preoperative diagnostic nasal endoscopy.
4. 0.6 or 0.7mm plain CT scan of the paranasal sinuses (coronal) has been added.
5. The NOSE scale is used to evaluate nasal blockage both before and after surgery.

6. A postoperative, diagnostic nasal endoscopy using 30 and 0 degree scopes has been carried out.

7. Post operatively patients are followed at 4 weeks and 6 weeks interval to assess the symptoms.

Sample size:

Using G*Power ver. 3.1.9.4 software for sample size calculation, The proportion of children of 13 years is 24%, and this study requires a sample size of 28. So to achieve a power of 80% for detecting a difference in Proportion (Exact – Proportion: Difference from constant (binomial test, one sample case)) with 5% level of significance.

Statistical Analysis:

The data obtained will be entered in a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analysis will be performed using statistical package for social sciences (Version 20). Results will be presented as Mean±SD, counts and percentages and diagrams. For normally distributed continuous variables between the two groups will be compared using independent t-test. For not normally distributed variables Mann Whitney U test will be used. Pre and post operative data will be compared using Paired t-test/Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Categorical variables between the two groups will be compared using a Chi-square test/Fisher's Exact test. Pre and Postoperative categorical data will be compared using Mac Nemer's chi-square test. $P < 0.05$ will hence be considered statistically significant. All statistical tests will perform two-tailed.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. symptomatic nasal obstruction due to moderate to severe degree of septal deviation
2. severe nasal septal deformity following trauma

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Septal Perforation
2. Moderate to severe adenoid hypertrophy
3. Allergic rhinitis
4. sinusitis

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

A hospital-based prospective study was conducted with 30 patients to study the effect of pediatric septoplasty and its outcomes , to identify the improvement in nasal obstruction and quality of improvement in nasal obstruction .

1. AGE DISTRIBUTION:

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
<=11	4	13.3
12-13	13	43.3
14	13	43.3

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON AGE

In our study out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for pediatric septoplasty 4(13.3%) patients were of <11 age, 13(43.3%) were between 12-13, 13(43.3%) were under 14 years.(TABLE 1)

2. SEX DISTRIBUTION:

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO SEX.

In our study out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for septoplasty, 23.3 % of the patients are females and 77% were males .(TABLE 2)

3. H/O TRAUMA:

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO H/O TRAUMA

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for septoplasty 16.7% of the patients had h/o trauma and 83.3 % had no h/o trauma .(TABLE 3)

4.SYMPTOMS OF ALLERGY:

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO THE PRESENCE OF SYMPTOMS OF ALLERGY:

Out of 30 patients in our study who were operated for septoplasty, 10% of the patients had symptoms of allergy ie., recurrent sneezing, watering of eyes.

(TABLE 4)

5.HEADACHE:

TABLE 5 : DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON THE PRESENCE OF HEADACHE

Out of 30 patients, in our study enrolled and operated for septoplasty, 23.3% of the patients had h/o headache.(TABLE 5)

6. SEPTUM:

SEPTUM	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
LEFT DNS	18	60
RIGHT DNS	11	36.7
LEFT DNS WITH SPUR	1	3.3

TABLE 6 : DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO DEVIATION OF SEPTUM

Out of 30 patients enrolled in our study, operated for septoplasty, 18 (60%) had left dns, 11(36.7%) had right dns, and 1(3.3%) had left dns with spur.(TABLE 6)

7.TURBINATES:

TABLE 7 : DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON THE HYPERTROPHY OF TURBINATE

Out of 30 patients enrolled in our study and operated for septoplasty, 33% had left ith, 44% had right ith, 23.3% had bilateral ITH.(TABLE 7)

8. PRE OPERATIVE NOSE SCALE SCORE:

SCALE	PRE OP NOSE SCORE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
SEVERE	75	2	6.7
	80	7	23.3
EXTREME	85	11	36.7
	90	8	26.7
	95	2	6.7

TABLE 8: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO PRE OP NOSE SCALE SCORE

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for septoplasty in our study, lowest pre op nose score was for 2 patients had 75 (severe) as nose score and 2 patients had highest nose score which was 95 (extreme).(TABLE 8).

9. PRE OPERATIVE VAS SCORE

VAS	SCORE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MODERATE(4)	7	4	13.3
SEVERE(26)	8	15	50
	9	11	36.7

TABLE 9 : DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO PRE OP VAS SCORE

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for septoplasty in our study, 4 patients had lowest VAS score (7 moderate) and 11 patients had highest VAS score (9 severe). (TABLE 9)

10. POD 7 NOSE SCALE SCORE:

SCALE	POD 7 NOSE SCORE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MODERATE	50	8	26.7
SEVERE	55	10	33.3
	60	9	30
	65	2	6.7
	70	1	3.3

TABLE 10 : DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO POD 7 NOSE SCALE SCORE

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for septoplasty in our study, on post op day 7, 8 patients had lowest nose score (50 moderate) and 1 patient had highest nose score (70 severe).(TABLE 10)

11. POD 6 WEEKS NOSE SCORE:

SCALE	POD 6 WEEKS NOSE SCORE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MILD	5	7	23.3
	15	9	30
	25	8	26.7
MODERATE	30	2	6.7

TABLE 11: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO POD 6 WEEKS NOSE SCALE SCORE

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for septoplasty, after 6 weeks of post op, 7 patients had lowest nose score(5 mild) and 2 had highest nose score (30 moderate). (TABLE 11)

12. POD 6 WEEKS VAS SCORE:

SCALE	VAS SCORE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MILD	0	3	10
	1	10	33.3
	2	7	23.3
	3	3	10
	4	1	3.3
MODERTE	5	3	10
	6	3	10

TABLE 12: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO POD 6 WEEKS VAS SCORE

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated in our study, 3 patients had lowest vas score of 0(mild) and 3 patients has highest vas score of 6 (moderate).(TABLE 12)

13. DESCRIPTIVE STASTISTICS:

NOSE SCALE	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	MEDIAN(25 TH -75 TH)	WILCOXON SIGNED RANK TEST	SIGNIFICANCE
PRE OP	85.7	5.167	85(80-90)	-4.826	0.0001
POD 6 WEEKS	5.83	3.957	5(5-6.25)		

TABLE 13: NOSE SCALE PRE OPERATIVELY AND 6 WEEKS POST OPERATIVELY

The mean pre op nose scale score was 85.7 and standard deviation is 5.167 and mean post op 6 weeks nose score was 5.83, standard deviation was 3.957. Nose scores of both the groups were compared using Wilcoxon signed ranks test (-4.826), and found to be Significant (p value <0.001).(TABLE 13)

14.VAS SCORE:

VAS SCALE	MEAN	STANDARD DEVAITION	MEDIAN(25TH-75TH)	WILCOXON SIGNED RANKS TEST	SIGNIFICANCE
PRE OP	8.233	6.7891	8(8-9)	-4.798	0.0001
POD 6 WEEKS	2.33	1.86313	2(1-3.25)		

TABLE 14: VAS SCORE PRE OPERATIVELY AND 6 WEEKS OPERATIVELY

The mean pre op vas score was 8.233 and the standard deviation was 6.7891 where as the post op 6 weeks vas score was 2.33, standard deviation was 1.86313. Vas scores of both the groups were compared using Wilcoxon signed rank test (-4.798) and found to be significant (p value <0.001). (TABLE 14)

15. COMPLICATIONS:

COMPLICATIONS		FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	NOTES
EARLY	EPISTAXIS	PRESENT -0	0	NOT REPORTED
		ABSENT- 100	100	
	SEPTAL HEMATOMA	PRESENT-0	0	NOT REPORTED
		ABSENT-100	100	
INTERMEDIATE	CRUSTING	PRESENT-8	26.7	DNE WITH DECRUSTATION AND SUCTION CLEARANCE
		ABSENT-22	73.3	
	VESTIBULITIS	PRESENT-3	10	MOSTLY DUE TO CRUSTATION
		ABSENT-27	90	
LATE	SYNECHIA	PRESENT-8	26.7	SYNECHIA RELEASE
		ABSENT-22	73.3	
	SEPTAL PERFORATION	PRESENT-0	0	NOT REPORTED
ABSENT-100		100		
	RESIDUAL DEVIATION	PRESENT-4	13.3	DUE TO LIMITED CARTILAGE REMOVAL
		ABSENT-26	86.7	

TABLE 15: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO COMPLICATIONS POST SURGERY

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated in our study, no patients had epistaxis, septal hematoma and septal perforation. 8 (26.7 %) patients had post op crusting and synechia, 3(10%) had vestibulitis, 4(13.3%) had residual deviation. (Table 15)

DISCUSSION

Paediatric septoplasty, in contrast to adult septoplasty, is still debatable and up for debate since it is thought that performing the procedure in underdeveloped nations may have negative consequences on the development of the nose and face. The most important aspect of surgery is to preserve the principal nasal and midface growth centres while performing a cautious excision of the cartilage. Excision should be kept to a minimum, and an excised segment must be reinserted after remodelling. Certain precautions in pediatric septoplasty should be considered to reduce the possible effect on nasal growth and shape. Minimal excision is recommended, and following remodelling, an excised segment needs to be reinserted. When performing paediatric septoplasty, there are a few measures that should be taken to lessen the potential impact on nasal growth and morphology.

These include avoiding the elevation of the nasal mucosa of the floor to avoid damage to the incisive nerves, avoidance of incision and excision through the growing and supporting zones, especially at the sphenothmoid dorsal zone, avoiding the separation of the septal cartilage from the perpendicular plate, avoidance of transecting the septospinal ligament, avoidance of unilateral or bilateral separation of the upper lateral cartilages from the septum, and to avoid implanting alloplastic or biomaterials in the growing septum. The incisive nerves should not be injured by elevating the nasal mucosa of the floor, cutting or excising through the growing and supporting zones, particularly at the sphenothmoid dorsal zone, separating the septal cartilage from the perpendicular plate, cutting through the septospinal ligament, separating the upper lateral cartilages from the septum unilaterally or bilaterally, or implanting biomaterials or alloplastic materials in the growing septum. We attempt to draw attention to a few issues pertaining to long-term outcomes following surgery and health-related quality of life in the current study. The danger of septoplasty on

the long-term growth of the face is low in certain paediatric children. Parents and young patients should be educated about long-term follow-up and the necessity of revision surgery after puberty, regardless of the type of nose surgery performed on their child.⁴⁹

INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS LITERATURE:

The total number of male and female patients in this study varied from a population of 30 patients with deviated nasal septum leading to symptomatic severe nasal obstruction who attended the ENT OPD during the study period who fulfilled the inclusion criteria .

ANALYSIS OF PATIENT PARAMETERS

1.AGE DISTRIBUTION:

The present study, included patients ranging from 10 TO 14 years of age . Out of 30 patients, 4 children were ≤ 11 years, 13 children were ranging between 12-13 years. 13 children were of 14 year age group. Mean age in this study is 12.73. On a contrary, in a study by Basil et al.,⁴⁸ mean age was 8.5. and it was 15.7 in a study by Manteghi et al.,⁴⁷

2.GENDER RATIO:

Out of 30 patients, 23.% were females, 76.7 % were males which shows that majority are males. This correlates with a study by Basil et al.,⁴⁸ in which males were 96.3% and a study by Sabry et al in which it was 70% .³¹

4.NASAL OBSTRUCTION:

All patients (100%) presented with nasal obstruction. Out of them 34% had right sided nasal obstruction, 38% had left sided nasal obstruction and 28% had b/l nasal

obstruction.

4.H/O TRAUMA :

Out of 30 patients enrolled and operated for septoplasty 16.7% of the patients had h/o trauma and 83.3 % had no h/o trauma

5. SYMPTOMS OF ALLERGY:

Out of 30 patients in our study who are operated for septoplasty, 10% of the patients had symptoms of allergy ie., recurrent sneezing, watering of eyes.

6.DNS:

Out of 30 patients enrolled in our study, operated for septoplasty, 18 (60%) had left dns, 11(36.7%) had right dns and 1(3.3%) had left dns with spur.

7.POST OP CRUSTING:

26.7% of the patients had crusting which correlates with study by Basil et al., in which it is 32%., which was cleared by meticulous suction clearance and instructing patient to do saline nasal douching.⁴⁸

8. SYNECHIA:

Synechia was seen in 26.7 % of the patients. In contrary it was 7% in study by Muhammad et al.,⁴⁹ .48% in a study by Basil et al.,⁴⁸

9.VESTIBULITIS:

It is seen only in 10% of the patients, where as it is 24% in a study by Basil et al.,⁴⁸

10 .ANALYSIS OF OUTCOMES OF THE SURGERY:

SEPTOPLASTY: In our study 30 patients had undergone septoplasty

11. COMPARISON BETWEEN PRE OP AND POST OP 6 WEEKS NOSE SCORE:

Pre op scores were ranging between 75 to 95 and out of 30, only 2 patients were under severe nose scale (75) and rest all were under extreme scale(80-95) . During follow up on 7th post operative day, there is improvement in nasal obstruction and nose score and scores were ranging between 50 and 70, that is 23 were under severe scale, and 7 were under moderate scale.

During further follow up after post op 6 weeks, there is significant improvement in nasal obstruction and nose score and scores were ranging between 0 to 30. Out of 30 patients, 26 were under mild and rest 4 were under moderate scale.

Pre op and pod 6 weeks scores were compared using Wilcoxon signed rank test Mean of total pre op scores of 30 patients was 85.17 and that of pod 6 weeks scores was 5.83. Z value is -4.826 and the results were statistically significant, $p < 0.0001$, These results correlate with a study Basil et al⁴⁸ on 25 patients in which the pre op nose score was 82.0 ± 7.9 , and an another study by et al.,²⁸ Where pre op score was 71 ± 18.9 , where the comparison of pre op and post op nose scores were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

12. COMPARISON BETWEEN PRE-OP AND POST OP 6 WEEKS VAS SCORE:

Pre op VAS scores were ranging between 7 and 9 and out of 30 patients 4 were under score 7(moderate), 15 were underscore 8(severe), 11 were under score 9(severe) which correlates with a study by Basil etal., in which 6 patients were under moderate pre op VAS score and 24 were under severe pre op VAS score.⁴⁸

During further follow up after post op 6 weeks, there is significant improvement in nasal obstruction and VAS score and scores were ranging between 0 to 6. Out of 30 patients, 4 were 0 score (mild). 7 were under score 5 (mild). 9 were under 15 (mild). 8 were under score (25). Only 2 were with score 30.

Pre op and pod 6 weeks VAS scores were compared using Wilcoxon signed rank test. Mean of total pre op scores of 30 patients was 8.233 and that of pod 6 weeks scores was 2.33. z value is -4.798 and the results were statistically significant, $p < 0.0001$, These results correlate with a study by Basil et al⁴⁸ in which the pre op vas score mean was 8.1 ± 0.85 in which the comparison of pre op and post op vas scores were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). So from this discussion, septoplasty in pediatric age group had benefited patients which correlated with other studies in terms of NOSE and VAS scores.

13.LIMITATIONS:

- 1.Lack of long term follow up of the patients is one of the limitations in this study. In the current study patients were followed post op 1week, 4 weeks and then 6 weeks.
- 2.VAS score was given by parents, since the patients were of pediatric age group. So, there might be a bias with regards to VAS score.

CONCLUSION

Septoplasty in pediatric age group (<14 years) has resulted in significant improvement with regards to nasal obstruction and also quality of life of children. There can be very few complications like crusting , synechia post surgery which can be easily addressed

REFERENCES :

1. Grymer L, Bosch C. The nasal septum and the development of the midface. A longitudinal study of a pair of monozygotic twins. *Rhinology*. 1997;35(1):6-10.
2. Gilbert J, Segal S. Growth of the Nose and the Septorhinoplastic Problem in Youth. *Plast Freer O. The Correction Of Deflections Of The Nasal Septum With A Minimum Of Traumatism. JAMA*. 1902;XXXVIII(10):636.
3. *Reconstr Surg*. 1959;23(3):293.
4. Farrior RT, Connolly ME. Septorhinoplasty in Children. *Otolaryngol Clin North Am* 1970;3:345-64.
5. Sarnat B, Wexler M. The Snout After Resection of Nasal Septum in Adult Rabbits. *Arch Otolaryngol*. 1967;86(4):463-466.
6. Hartshorn DF. Facial Growth Effects of Nasal Septal Cartilage Resection in Beagle Pups. Iowa City, IA: University of Iowa Press; 1970.
7. Bernstein L. Early submucous resection of nasal septal cartilage: a pilot study in canine pups. *Arch Otolaryngol*. 1973;97(3):273-278.
8. Cupero T, Middleton C, Silva A. Effects of Functional Septoplasty on the Facial Growth of Ferrets. *Arch Otolaryngol*. 2001;127(11):1367.
9. Triglia JM, Cannoni M, Pech A. Septorhinoplasty in children: Benefits of the external approach. *J Otolaryngol* 19:274-278, 1990.
10. Jugo S. Total Septal Reconstruction Through Decortication (External) Approach in Children. *Arch Otolaryngol*. 1987;113(2):173-178.
11. Bejar I, Farkas LG, Messner AH, and Crysdale WS. Nasal growth after external septoplasty in children. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 122:816-821, 1996
12. El-Hakim H, Crysdale W, Abdollel M, Farkas L. A Study of Anthropometric Measures Before and After External Septoplasty in Children. *Arch Otolaryngol*. 2001;127(11):1362.
13. Walker PJ, Crysdale WS, and Farkas LG. External septorhinoplasty in children: Outcome and effect on growth of septal excision and reimplantation. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 119:984-989, 1993.
14. Tasca I, and Compadretti GC. Nasal growth after pediatric septoplasty at long-term follow-up. *Am J Rhinol Allergy* 25:e7-e12, 2011.
15. Tatum S. *Pediatric Facial And Reconstructive Surgery, An Issue Of Facial Plastic Surgery Clinics Of North America, E-Book.*; 2014:503-508.
16. Vetter U, Pirsig W, Helbing G, et al. Patterns of growth in human septal cartilage: A review of new approaches. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol* 7:63-74, 1984.
17. Verwoerd C, Verwoerd-Verhoef H. Rhinosurgery in Children: Basic Concepts. *Facial Plastic Surgery*. 2007;23(4):219-230.
18. Kawalski H, Śpiwak P. How septum deformations in newborns occur. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 1998;44(1):23-30.
19. Christophel JJ, and Gross CW. Pediatric septoplasty. *Otolaryngol Clin North Am* 42:287-294, ix, 2009.
20. Alshaikh N, Lo S. Nasal septal abscess in children: From diagnosis to management and prevention. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2011;75(6):737-744.
21. D'Ascanio L, Lancione C, Pompa G, et al. Craniofacial growth in children with nasal septum deviation: A cephalometric comparative study. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol* 74:1180-1183, 2010.
22. Blahova O. Late results of nasal septum injury in children. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol* 10:137-141, 1985.
23. Levi J, McKee-Cole K, Barth P, Brody R, Reilly J. Outcomes of recalcitrant idiopathic epistaxis in children: Septoplasty as a surgical treatment. *Laryngoscope*. 2016;126(12):2833-2837.

24. Boenisch M, Tamas H, Nolst Trenite GJ. Influence of polydioxanone foil on growing septal cartilage after surgery in an animal model: new aspects of cartilage healing and regeneration (preliminary results). *Arch Facial Plast Surg*. 2003 Jul-Aug;5(4):316-9.
25. Menger DJ, Tabink IC, Nolst Trenite GJ. Nasal Septal Abscess in Children: Reconstruction with Autologous Cartilage Grafts on Polydioxanone Plate. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2008 Aug;134(8):842-7. doi: 10.1001/archotol.134.8.842.
26. Healy G, Tardy M. Septorhinoplasty in children. *Operative Techniques in Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery*. 1994;5(1):22-26.
27. Stewart MG, Witsell DL, Smith TL, Weaver EM, Yueh B, Hannley MT, Development and validation of the nasal obstruction symptom evaluation (NOSE) scale, *Head Neck Surg*. 130 (2004) 157–163.
28. Yilmaz M, Guven M, Akidil O, Kayabasoglu G, Demir D, Mermer H. Does septoplasty improve the quality of life in children?. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2014;78(8):1274-1276.
29. Can İ, Ceylan K, Bayiz Ü, Ölmez A, Samim E. Acoustic rhinometry in the objective evaluation of childhood septoplasties. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2005;69(4)
30. Lawrence R. Pediatric septoplasty: a review of the literature. *International journal of pediatric otorhinolaryngology*. 2012 Aug 1;76(8):1078-81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijporl.2012.04.020>
31. Sabry O, Dewidar H, Abdel Aziz M, Elemam A, Nassar A. Efficiency of modified Goldman's technique in open pediatric septoplasty. *The Egyptian Journal of Otolaryngology*. 2021 Dec;37(1):1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43163-021-00074-0>
32. Resende L, Carmo CD, Mocellin L, Pasinato R, Mocellin M. Disease-specific quality of life after septoplasty and bilateral inferior turbinate outfracture in patients with nasal obstruction. *Brazilian journal of otorhinolaryngology*. 2018 Sep;84:591-8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjorl.2017.07.001>
33. Justicz N, Choi S. When Should Pediatric Septoplasty Be Performed for Nasal Airway Obstruction?. *The Laryngoscope*. 2019 Jul;129(7):1489-90. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lary.27602>
34. Anderson K, Ritchie K, Chorney JM, Bezuhly M, Hong P. The impact of septoplasty on health related quality of life in paediatric patients. *Clinical Otolaryngology*. 2016 Apr;41(2):144-8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/coa.12485>
35. Calvo-Henríquez, C., Neves, J.C., Arancibia Tagle, D. et al. Does pediatric septoplasty compromise midfacial growth? A systematic review. *Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol* 277, 1565–1574 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00405-020-05919-7>
36. El-Hakim H, Crysdale WS, Abdollel M, Farkas LG. A study of anthropometric measures before and after external septoplasty in children: a preliminary study. *Archives of Otolaryngology–Head & Neck Surgery*. 2001 Nov 1;127(11):1362-6. doi:10.1001/archotol.127.11.1362
37. Béjar I, Farkas LG, Messner AH, Crysdale WS. Nasal growth after external septoplasty in children. *Archives of Otolaryngology–Head & Neck Surgery*. 1996 Aug 1;122(8):816-21. doi:10.1001/archotol.1996.01890200008002
38. Kawai, K., Dombrowski, N., AuYeung, T. and Adil, E.A. (2021), Validation of the Nasal Obstruction Symptom Evaluation Scale in Pediatric Patients. *The Laryngoscope*, 131: E2594–E2598. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lary.29420>
39. Stewart MG, Smith TL, Weaver EM, et al. Outcomes after Nasal Septoplasty: Results from the Nasal Obstruction Septoplasty Effectiveness (NOSE) Study. *Otolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery*. 2004;130(3):283–290. doi:10.1016/j.otohns.2003.12.004
40. Lee VS, Gold RM, Parikh SR. Short-term quality of life outcomes following pediatric septoplasty. *Acta oto-laryngologica*. 2017 Mar 4;137(3):293-6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00016489.2016.1229023>
41. Tasca I, Compadretti GC. Nasal growth after pediatric septoplasty at long-term follow-up. *American journal of rhinology & allergy*. 2011 Jan;25(1):e7-12. <https://doi.org/10.2500/ajra.2011.25.3536>

42. Gary CC. Pediatric nasal surgery: timing and technique. *Current opinion in otolaryngology & head and neck surgery*. 2017 Aug 1;25(4):286-90. doi: 10.1097/MOO.0000000000000378
43. Cingi C, Muluk NB, Ulusoy S, Lopatin A, Sahin E, Passali D, Bellussi L, Atilla H, Hanci D, Altintoprak N, Rusetski Y. Septoplasty in children. *American journal of rhinology & allergy*. 2016 Mar;30(2):e42-7. <https://doi.org/10.2500/ajra.2016.30.4289>
44. Bishop R, Sethia R, Allen D, Elmaraghy CA. Pediatric nasal septoplasty outcomes. *Translational Pediatrics*. 2021 Nov;10(11):2883. doi: 10.21037/tp-21-359.
45. Kopacheva-Barsova G, Nik olovski N. Justification for rhinoseptoplasty in children—our 10 years overview. *Open access Macedonian journal of medical sciences*. 2016 Sep 15;4(3):397. doi: 10.3889/oamjms.2016.080.
46. Martins MBB, Lima RG de, Lima FVF de, Barreto VMP, Santos ACG, Santos Júnior RC. Demystifying Septoplasty in Children. *Int Arch Otorhinolaryngol. Int. Arch. Otorhinolaryngol.*, 2014 18(1):054–6. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s.0033-1358576>
47. Manteghi A, Din H, Bundogji N, Leuin SC. Pediatric septoplasty and functional septorhinoplasty: A quality of life outcome study. *International journal of pediatric otorhinolaryngology*. 2018 Aug 1;111:16-20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijporl.2018.05.016>.
48. Basil Mohammednather Saeed* , Mohammed Saeed Sheet** , Emanuel Sargon Emanuel**
*Department of Surgery, College of Medicine, University of Mosul , **Otolaryngology Department , Al-Sheikhan General Hospital, Mosul Iraq Correspondence: basil.saeed@uomosul.edu.iq , basil.saeed@yahoo.com
49. Muhammad IA, Rahman NU. Complications of the surgery for deviated nasal septum. *Journal of the College of Physicians and Surgeons--Pakistan: JCPSP*. 2003 Oct 1;13(10):565-8. doi:10.2003/jcpsp.565568.

ANNEXURE I

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956

Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 710/2022-23

30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "A STUDY OF PEDIATRIC NASAL SEPTOPLASTY AND ITS OUTCOMES".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. Surekha Reddy, PG, Dept. of ENT.

NAME OF THE GUIDE: Dr. H.T. Lathadevi, Professor, Dept. of ENT

Dr.Santoshkumar Jeevanagi
Chairperson
IEC-SBMPMC,
VIJAYAPURA

Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr.Akram A. Naikawadi
Member Secretary
IEC-SBMPMC,
VIJAYAPURA

MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization.

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.

BLDE (DU): Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263303, Website: www.bldedu.ac.in, E-mail: office@bldedu.ac.in

College: Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263019, E-mail: bmpmc.principal@bldedu.ac.in

ANNEXURE – II

PROFORMA

- 1) NAME: 2) CASE NO:
- 3) AGE: 4) IPD NO:
- 5) SEX 6) DOA:
- 7) RELIGION: 8) DOS:
- 9) OCCUPATION: 10) DOD:
- 11) RESIDENCE: 12) CHIEF COMPLAINTS:
- 13) HISTORY OF PRESENTING ILLNESS:
- 14) PAST HISTORY:
- Diabetes mellitus
 - Hypertension
 - History of any previous surgery.
 - Usage of Ototoxic drugs
- 15) FAMILY HISTORY:

16) GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

Pallor: Present/Absent Icterus: Present/Absent

Clubbing: Present/Absent

Generalized Lymphadenopathy: Present/Absent

Build: Poor/Medium /Well Nourishment: Poor / Medium /
Well

17) VITALS

PR:

BP:

RR:

Temp:

18) OTHER SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION:

- Respiratory System
- Cardiovascular System
- Central Nervous System
- Per Abdomen examination

19) LOCAL EXAMINATION

• EAR Right Left

Pinna

Pre auricular area

Post auricular area

Infra auricular area

External auditory canal

Tympanic membrane:

Pars Tensa

Pars flaccida

Mastoid Tenderness :

Fistula sign

Tragal Tenderness

Facial nerve function

Nystagmus

Tuning Fork test

Rinnes

Webers

ABC

• NOSE:

On tip elevation

Columella, vestibule:

Right

Left

Nasal cavity:

Nasal Mucosa

Septum:

Turbinates:

Examination of PNS:

- ORAL CAVITY :

- OROPHARYNX:

20) INVESTIGATION:

BLOOD ROUTINE:

URINE ROUTINE:

CBC

BT CT

URINE ROUTINE

XRAY PNS / CT PNS

21) INFERENCE:

COMMENTS

ANNEXURE –III

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

BLDE (deemed to be university)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND
RESEARCH CENTRE , VIJAYAPURA- 586103.**

TITLE OF THE PROJECT

**“STUDY OF PEDIATRIC SEPTOPLASTY AND ITS
OUTCOMES”**

PG STUDENT - Dr. SUREKHA

DEPARTMENT OF

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

PG GUIDE DR.H.T.LATHADEVI

DEPARTMENT OF OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

BLDE (Deemed To Be University)

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPURA – 586103

All aspects of this consent form are explained to the patient in the language understood by him/her

1) PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed about this study. I have also been given a free choice of participation in this study.

2) PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this study.

3) RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

4) BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to improve survival of patient and will bring about a better outcome.

5) CONFIDENTIALITY:

6) PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed about this study. I have also been given a free choice of participation in this study.

7) PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this study.

8) RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

8) BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to improve survival of the patient and will bring about a better outcome.

9) CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of Hospital records and will be subject to the confidentiality and privacy regulation. Information of a sensitive personal nature will not be a part of the medical records, but will be stored in the investigator's research file and identified only by a code number. The code-key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate location. If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose, no name will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or videotapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photographs and videotapes and hear the audiotapes before giving this permission.

11) REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time. Dr. SUREKHA is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation. If during the study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

12) REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital. I also understand that DR. SUREKHA may terminate my participation in the study after she has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or physical therapist, if this is appropriate.

13) INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

14) REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time. Dr. SUREKHA is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation. If during the study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

15) REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital. I also understand that DRSUREKHA may terminate my participation in the study after she has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or physical therapist, if this is appropriate.

16) INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits to the best of my ability in patient's own language.

Dr. SUREKHA

(Investigator)

Date:

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT

I confirm that DR.SUREKHA has explained to me the purpose of research, the study procedures that I will undergo, and the possible risks and discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my own language. I have read and I understand this consent form. Therefore, I agree to give consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

Participant / Guardian

Date

Witness to signature

Date

ANNEXURE IV

KEY TO MASTER CHART

PT	PATIENT
IP NO	IN PATIENT NUMBER
RT	RIGHT
LT	LEFT
DNS	DEVIATED NASAL SEPTUM
ITH	INFERIOR TURBINATE HYPERTROPHY
PRE OP	PRE OPERATIVE
POST OP	POST OPERATIVE
POD	POST OPERATIVE DAY

MASTER CHART :

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
1	pt name	lp no	age	sex	nasal obstruction	mouth breathing	snoring	nasal discharge	trauma to nose	bleeding from nose	loss of smell	sneezing	itching of nose	wartering of eyes	symptoms of allergy
2	sachin	32619	14	male	present	absent	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
3	srujan	321923	11	male	present	present	absent	present	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
4	pruthviraj	392489	14	male	present	absent	absent	absent	yes	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
5	savitri	400379	14	female	present	absent	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
6	kashim	613722	14	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
7	prajwal	26933	13	male	present	absent	absent	absent	no	present	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
8	bhagyasree	44098	14	female	present	absent	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
9	shivkumar	68181	14	male	present	present	absent	absent	yes	present	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
10	vijay	153299	12	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
11	pradeep	145037	14	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
12	saptkumar	139427	13	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
13	samarth	164740	12	male	presnt	present	absent	absent	yes	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
14	thomas	140710	10	male	present	absent	absent	present	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
15	raju	160520	11	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	present	present	present	present
16	anjali	614560	14	female	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
17	beerappa	246797	13	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	present	present	present	present
18	veeresh	235675	12	male	present	present	absent	present	no	absent	absent	present	absent	absent	absent
19	satish	234687	12	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
20	geetha	982346	11	female	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	present	present	present	present
21	syed	235986	14	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
22	sufian	863468	14	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
23	akhil	123765	13	male	present	present	absent	present	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
24	basavaraj	167543	12	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
25	gowtham	154235	12	male	present	absent	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
26	srivani	145695	14	female	present	present	absent	absent	yes	present	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
27	pundalik	324566	13	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
28	madan	982566	12	male	present	present	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
29	sravathi	142345	14	female	present	present	absent	present	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
30	prashanth	875798	13	male	present	absent	absent	absent	no	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent
31	siri	241320	14	female	present	present	absent	absent	yes	present	absent	absent	absent	absent	absent

	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA
1	post nasal drip	headache	facial pain	nasal mucosa	septum	turbinates	surgery	pre op nasal congestion	pre op nasal blockage	pre op trouble breathing	pre op trouble sleeping	pre op obstruction during exertion
2	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	4	3
3	absent	present	absent	congested	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	4	3
4	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns	b/l ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	4	3
5	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	right ith	septoplasty	3	4	4	4	3
6	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns with left spur	left ith	septoplasty	4	4	4	4	3
7	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	4	4	4	3
8	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	4	4	4	3	3
9	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns	b/l ith	septoplasty	3	3	3	3	3
10	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	4	4	4	3
11	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	3	4	3	3
12	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	b/l ith	septoplasty	4	3	3	4	3
13	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	3	3	4	3	3
14	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	3	4	4	3
15	absent	present	absent	normal	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	4	4	3	3	3
16	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	b/l ith	septoplasty	3	4	4	4	3
17	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	3	3
18	absent	present	absent	congested	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	3	3
19	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	4	3	4	3	3
20	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	right ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	3	3
21	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	b/l ith	septoplasty	3	4	4	4	3
22	absent	present	absent	normal	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	3	3	3	4	3
23	absent	present	absent	congested	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	3	3	4	4	3
24	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	4	3
25	absent	present	absent	normal	left dns	b/l ith	septoplasty	3	4	4	3	3
26	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	3	4	4	3
27	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	Right ith	septoplasty	3	4	3	3	3
28	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	4	3	4	4	3
29	absent	present	absent	congested	left dns	b/l ith	septoplasty	3	4	4	4	4
30	absent	absent	absent	normal	left dns	right ith	septoplasty	3	3	3	3	3
31	absent	absent	absent	normal	right dns	left ith	septoplasty	4	4	3	4	3
	AB	AC	AD	AE	AF	AG	AH					
	pre op total nose score		pod 1 nasal congestion	pod 1 nasal blockage	pod 1 trouble breathing through nose	pod 1 trouble sleeping	pod 1 obstruction during exertion					
	85 extreme		4	4	3	4	3					
	85 extreme		4	4	3	3	3					
	85 extreme		3	3	3	4	2					
	90 extreme		3	3	2	4	3					
	95 extreme		3	3	3	4	3					
	90 extreme		3	3	3	3	3					
	90 extreme		4	3	3	4	3					
	75 severe		4	3	3	4	3					
	90 extreme		4	3	2	3	3					
	80 extreme		4	3	3	4	3					
	85 extreme		4	3	3	3	3					
	80 extreme		4	3	3	4	3					
	85 extreme		3	3	3	4	2					
	85 extreme		3	3	3	4	3					
	90 extreme		3	3	3	4	2					
	80 extreme		4	3	3	4	3					
	80 extreme		3	3	3	3	3					
	85 extreme		3	3	3	4	3					
	80 extreme		3	3	3	3	3					
	75 severe		4	3	3	4	3					
	90 extreme		3	3	2	3	3					
	90 extreme		4	3	3	4	3					

pod 1 total nose score		pod 1 week nasal congestion	pod 1 week nasal blockage	pod 1 week trouble breathing	pod 1 week trouble sleeping	pod 1week obstruction during exertion
	90 extreme	3	3	3	3	2
	85 extreme	2	2	2	2	2
	75 severe	2	3	2	2	1
	75 severe	2	3	3	3	2
	85 extreme	3	3	2	2	2
	75 severe	3	2	2	3	2
	85 extreme	2	3	2	3	2
	85 extreme	3	2	2	2	2
0	75 severe	2	3	2	2	2
1	80 extreme	3	3	2	2	2
2	80 extreme	3	2	2	3	2
3	85 extreme	2	2	2	3	1
4	75 severe	3	2	2	3	2
5	80 extreme	3	2	2	3	1
5	75 severe	2	2	2	2	2
7	75 severe	2	2	3	3	3
3	75 severe	2	2	2	2	2
3	80 extreme	2	3	2	3	1
0	75 severe	2	2	2	2	2
1	80 extreme	2	2	2	2	2
2	75 severe	3	2	2	2	2
3	85 extreme	2	2	2	2	2
4	85 extreme	3	2	2	2	2
5	70 severe	3	3	2	2	2
5	85 extreme	2	2	2	2	2
7	75 severe	3	2	2	3	1
3	85 extreme	3	3	2	2	2
3	65 severe	3	2	2	2	2
0	85 extreme	3	3	2	2	1
1	70 severe	2	2	2	2	2

total pod 1week nose score		pod 4weeks nasal congestion	pod 4 weeks nasal blockage	pod 4weeks trouble breathing	pod 4 weeks trouble sleeping
	70 severe	2	2	2	2
	50 moderate	2	2	2	1
	50 moderate	1	1	1	1
	65 severe	1	1	1	1
	60 severe	1	1	1	1
	60 severe	1	1	1	1
	60 severe	1	1	0	1
	55 severe	1	1	1	0
0	55 severe	1	1	2	0
1	60 severe	2	1	1	1
2	60 severe	1	1	1	1
1	55 severe	1	1	1	1
1	60 severe	1	1	1	1
3	55 severe	1	2	1	1
3	60 severe	1	1	2	1
7	65 severe	2	2	1	1
3	50 moderate	1	1	1	1
3	55 severe	1	2	1	1
0	50 moderate	2	1	1	2
1	50 severe	2	2	2	1
2	55 severe	1	1	1	2
1	50 moderate	2	2	1	1
1	55 severe	2	2	1	1
1	60 severe	2	1	1	1
3	50 moderate	2	2	1	1
7	55 severe	2	1	1	1
3	60 severe	2	2	1	1
3	55 severe	2	1	1	1
0	55 severe	2	2	1	1
1	50 moderate	2	1	1	1

pod 4 weeks obstruction during exertion	pod 4weeks nose score		pod 6 weeks nasal congestion	pod 6 weeks nasal blockage	pod 6 weeks trouble breathing
1	45 moderate		0	0	0
1	40 moderate		0	0	0
1	25 mild		0	0	1
1	25 mild		0	0	1
1	25 mild		1	0	0
1	25 mild		0	0	1
1	20 mild		1	0	0
1	20 mild		0	0	0
1	20 mild		1	1	0
1	30 moderate		0	0	0
1	25 mild		1	0	0
1	25 mild		1	0	0
1	25 mild		0	0	1
1	30 moderate		0	0	1
0	25 mild		1	0	1
1	35 moderate		1	0	0
1	25 mild		0	0	1
0	20 mild		1	0	0
1	35 moderate		0	0	1
1	40 moderate		1	1	0
1	30 moderate		1	0	1
0	30 moderate		0	0	1
1	35 moderate		1	1	0
1	30 moderate		0	0	1
1	35 moderate		1	0	0
0	25 mild		1	0	0
1	35 moderate		0	0	1
1	30 moderate		0	0	0
0	30 moderate		0	0	1
0	25 mild		0	0	1

pod 6 weeks trouble breathing	pod 6 weeks trouble sleeping	pod 6 weeks obstruction during exertion	pod 6weeks nose score	pod 6 total nose score
0	1	1		10 mild
0	0	0		0 free from symptoms
1	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
0	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
0	0	0		5 mild
0	0	0		0 free from symptoms
0	0	0		10 mild
0	0	0		0 free from symptoms
0	0	0		5 mild
0	1	0		10 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		10 mild
0	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
0	0	0		5 mild
0	0	0		10 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
0	1	1		20 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
0	0	1		10 mild
0	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		5 mild
0	0	0		0 free from symptoms
1	0	0		5 mild
1	0	0		5 mild

Similarity Report ID: oid:3618:62491692

PAPER NAME

**21BMENT04-Surekah-08.07.2024 (1).do
cx**

AUTHOR

Surekha Reddy

WORD COUNT

9836 Words

CHARACTER COUNT

54599 Characters

PAGE COUNT

58 Pages

FILE SIZE

681.6KB

SUBMISSION DATE

Jul 8, 2024 10:20 AM GMT+5:30

REPORT DATE

Jul 8, 2024 10:21 AM GMT+5:30

● 9% Overall Similarity

The combined total of all matches, including overlapping sources, for each database.

- 7% Internet database
- 5% Publications database
- Crossref database
- Crossref Posted Content database
- 1% Submitted Works database

● Excluded from Similarity Report

- Bibliographic material
- Quoted material
- Cited material
- Abstract
- Methods and Materials
- Small Matches (Less than 14 words)

